

Government Performance On Property Tax Services Of Rural And Urban Areas In Ternate City

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Abstract: This study is intended to measure the performance of the Ternate City government in the service of property tax (PBB-P2) in rural and urban areas through the Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency (BP2RD). In this case, it is directly related to the object of research on the PBB-P2 tax Service (PBB-P2). This research was collecting data about actual problems about the symptoms that occur in the field, then through descriptive methods produced a precise and systematic description. Primary data is obtained through direct interviews with informants selected according to the quality and quantity of data needed. While secondary data is obtained through literature, legislation, websites on the internet and related documents. Furthermore, the data were analyzed according to Miles and Huberman, through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results show that in general the government's performance on the Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency in 2017 has not been maximized. There is still a lack of public participation in the management and PBB-P2 payments so that there are still many arrears from year to year. There is still a lack of socialization so that some people do not understand the benefits and risks of not paying PBB-P2.

Index Terms: Public services, property tax, government performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Approximately 70% of Indonesia's state budget is sourced from tax revenues, and the types of taxes that exist in Indonesia are now diverse. Although the rural and urban property taxes (PBB-P2) are not the most significant contributors to the state revenue from the tax sector, the PBB-P2 taxes has unique characteristics compared to other types of taxes. This difference can be seen from the number of taxpayers in this type of tax more than other types of taxes. The number of taxpayers in PBB-P2 includes all Indonesian citizens who own land and buildings in the territory of Indonesia. The current era of autonomy, demands its regions to be creative in finding sources of income that can finance the expenditure of local governments, to organize government and development. Thus the local government is not only required to be able to organize government, development and community service but is financially able to finance all of its needs. Implementation of Regional Autonomy needs to emphasize the principles of democracy, community participation, equity, justice and accountability and pay attention to the potential and diversity of the region. Therefore the government issued a law which regulates the regional government, namely Law No. 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government. Since the enactment of the Law, the Regional Government is the organizer of government affairs by the regional government and the Regional People's Legislative Assembly, according to the principle of autonomy and the task of assisting with the broadest principle of autonomy, in the system and principles of the Unitary Republic of Indonesia.

Regional autonomy is the Right, Authority and Obligation of the Autonomous Region to regulate and administer its government affairs and the interests of the local community in the system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. Autonomous regions are required to fund their households as much as possible from their economic potentials which are summarized in Regional Original Revenues (PAD) which include Regional Tax Results, Regional Retribution Results, Separate Regional Wealth Management Results, and other legitimate Regional Original Income. Local tax is a mandatory contribution to the area owned by an individual or a compelling entity based on the law, by not getting compensation directly and used for local purposes for the greatest prosperity of the people. Each region is given the same type of income source, but that does not mean that each region has the same amount of income in financing its authority. Regional income depends on the conditions owed by each region, for example, the population, area, regional wealth, and the level of economic growth in each region. The granting of authority to the areas to collect local taxes and levies has resulted in the collection of various types of regional taxes and levies that are related to multiple aspects of community life. The community must understand this collection as a source of revenue needed by the region to improve community welfare. Ternate City is one of the North Maluku Province regions which has a faster center of government, economy, infra-structure development and population growth compared to other regency/cities in North Maluku Province [1-4]. As time goes by, if the population growth in Ternate City increases, the higher the need for housing. If the higher the community's need for shelter, the higher the role of employees of the BP2RD Ternate City in collecting PBB-P2. Based on Ternate City regional regulation number 6 (2016) concerning main duty and the function of the local tax and retribution management agency (BP2RD) of Ternate City, the PBB-P2 is one type of tax that is administered by BP2RD Ternate City, which in implementation is based on the regional regulation Ternate City number 5 of 2013 concerning Land and Rural and Urban Building Taxes (PBB-P2). Significant factors affecting taxpayers to carry out PBB-P2 payments are payment service systems and procedures. Payment service systems and methods are too complicated, systems that are not well integrated, many

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additional requirements are made urgent, time is taken up only for tax payments, so people become bored waiting for the process of payment of land taxes and rural, urban buildings. Poor service systems and procedures so that there is a lack of public awareness to pay taxes. This can be seen in the BP2RD evaluation meeting in Ternate City that there are still substantial tax arrears in each village every year.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Service

Every activity carried out by the government against some people who have every beneficial activity in a group or unit and offer satisfaction even though the results are not bound to a product physically referred to as public service [5] [6]. Public services are defined as all forms of services, both in the form of public goods and public services which in principle are the responsibility and carried out by government agencies in the Center, in the Region, and in the environment of state-owned enterprises or regionally-owned enterprises, in an effort to fulfillment of the needs of the community and in the framework of implementing the provisions of the legislation [7]. Another definition, public service is the state's efforts to fulfill the basic needs and civil rights of every citizen of goods, services and administrative services provided by public service providers. The 1945 Indonesian Constitution mandates the state to fulfill the basic needs of every citizen for their welfare so that the effectiveness of a government system is primarily determined by the excellent and inadequate implementation of public services [8]. Meanwhile, Public Services is said to be the needs of the people for services varying according to the diversity of existing communities [9] [10]. The government is required to be able to provide a variety of services because the needs of the population are also diverse. Public Service is defined as the provision of services the needs of people who have an interest in the organization following the basic rules or procedures that have been established. Furthermore, according to Decree of the Minister of Administrative Reform No.63/KEP/M.PAN/7/2003, the public is all service activities carried out by public service providers as an effort to fulfill the needs of the recipient of services and the implementation of statutory provisions. Thus the public service is the fulfillment of the wishes and requirements of the community by the State organizers. The public, of course, establishes the state with the aim of improving the welfare of the people. In essence, the state, in this case, the government must be able to meet the needs of the people.

Principles of Public Service

The principles of organizing public services include [8]; a) legal certainty is meant by the existence of laws and regulations that guarantee the implementation of public services in accordance with the needs and sense of public justice; b) openness means that each service recipient can easily access and obtain information about the desired function; c) participatory is intended to encourage community participation in the delivery of public services by paying attention to the aspirations, needs and expectations of the community; d) accountability is intended that the process of implementing public services must be accountable in accordance with the provisions of the legislation; e) the public interest is designed that in the provision of public services it is not permissible to prioritize personal and/or class interests; f) professionalism

means that service providers must have competencies that are appropriate to their field of duty; g) equality of rights is intended that in providing public services it is not discriminatory in the sense of not differentiating ethnicity, race, religion, class, gender and economic status; i) the balance of rights and obligations means that the fulfillment of rights must be proportional to the obligations that must be carried out by both the provider and recipient of the service. To realize the general principles of good governance and the principles of public service, efforts are needed to develop government bureaucratic institutions, apparatus human resources and the quality of the process of organizing public services.

Public Service Standards

Public service must have service standards and be published as a guarantee of certainty for service recipients. Service standards are measures that must be possessed in the delivery of public services that must be obeyed by the service provider and recipient. Public service standards at least include; 1) service procedures are one of the public service standards. Service procedures must be standardized for providers and recipients of public services, including complaints so that problems do not occur in the future. Service procedures must be determined through minimum service standards so that the service recipient can understand the mechanism; 2) completion time is one of the public service standards. The settlement time is set from the time of submission of the application until the completion of the service including the complaint. The sooner the completion time of the service will increase the public's trust in the services provided; 3) service products are one of the public service standards. The results of the service will be accepted following the stipulated conditions. Service products must be well understood so that it needs socialization in the community; 4) service costs are one of the public service standards. Service costs including the details must be determined consistently, and there should be no discrimination because it will cause mistrust of the recipient of the service to the service provider. This service fee must be transparent on every service that will be provided to the community, so that it does not cause anxiety, especially to parties or communities who are less fortunate; 5) facilities and infrastructure are one of the public service standards. Provision of adequate service facilities and infrastructure by public service providers is crucial in determining and supporting the success of service delivery, and 6) the competence of service providers is one of the public service standards. The competency of service providers must be determined precisely based on the knowledge, skills, skills, attitudes and behaviors needed so that the quality of services provided.

Government Performance Concept

Each institution has a target or achievement of the desired work program in achieving its goals. The concept can be referred to like the concept of performance in carrying out government functions. Performance is primarily the work quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties according to the responsibilities given to him. In this case, employees can learn how much their performance is through means of information such as good comments from partners. However, performance appraisal refers to a formal and structured system that measures, assesses and influences the behavioral and outcome-related traits including

absence rates. Performance in the organization is the answer to the success or failure of the stated organizational goals. Civil servants often do not pay attention unless it is nasty or everything goes awry. Too often employees don't know how poor performance has deteriorated so that organizations within a government agency face a severe crisis. Government performance indicators consist of several components [9], including productivity, service quality, responsiveness, responsibility, and accountability. Government performance means a group of people in the organization with the authority and responsibility of each to achieve goals or a group of people and individuals, namely civil servants who are in government agencies or institutions that carry out government functions or tasks. Wrong impressions of profound organizations result in and ignore signs of warning of deteriorating performance. Performance is the result of work achieved by a person or group of people in an organization following their respective responsibilities and authorities. To complete the objectives of the organization legally, it does not violate the law and is following morals and ethics [11]. Performance is a result of work achieved by a person in carrying out tasks that are charged to him based on skills, experience and sincerity and time [12]. Completing the performance of the state apparatus must have the skills, knowledge, trustworthiness and time to be able to walk as expected in an organization or government agency to be used in explaining performance objectives and standards and motivating the performance of employees. Through measurement and performance evaluation can be determined by the level of success and failure of the organization in achieving its goals. For each organization, assessment of performance is a significant activity. This assessment can be used as a measure of the success of an organization within a specified period. The evaluation is also an input for the improvement or improvement of subsequent organizational performance [13].

Regional Taxes and Taxes

According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 28 of 2009, the local tax hereinafter referred to as tax is the taxpayer's contribution to the area owed by a person or body that is compelling based on the Law, by not getting immediate compensation and being used for regional purposes for as much as - the magnitude of people's prosperity. Taxes have the following elements: Contributions from the people to the state, the right to collect taxes is the state, the contributions are in the form of money, not goods [14]. Without reciprocal services or counterparts from a country that can be directly demonstrated, in the payment of taxes cannot be shown the existence of individual counter-achievements by the government. Used to finance state households, namely expenditures that benefit the broader community. The tax function is funding which is also called the primary purpose of the tax, or fiscal capacity. That is the tax is used as a tool to optimally enter funds into the State treasury based on the applicable Tax Law [15]. The regulatory function which is also called an additional role, namely tax is used as a tool to achieve specific goals that are located outside the financial field. The conditions for tax collection must be fair (conditions of justice) in legislation including taxation in general and evenly distributed, and adjusted to their respective abilities. Tax collection must be based on the Law (juridical conditions) in Indonesia tax regulated in the 1945 Indonesian Constitution

article 23 paragraph 2, and this provides legal guarantees to declare justice both for the country and its citizens [14]. Not disrupting the economy collection may not interfere with the smooth activities of production and trade, so as not to cause a slowdown in the economy of the community. Tax collection must be efficient (financial requirements) according to the budgetary function, and the tax collection fee must be reduced so that it is lower than the revenue. The tax collection system must be simple to facilitate and encourage people to fulfill their tax obligations. The difference in the division or classification of taxes is based on a criterion, the following is the division of the type of tax based on these criteria is according to the group consisting of direct taxes, namely taxes that are directly charged to taxpayers who are obliged to pay taxes and indirect taxes, namely taxes that can be transferred to other parties [15]. According to its nature which consists of personal taxes, namely taxes whose first time is considered is the subject of the tax and real tax, namely the tax at the time of its imposition, the first object is the object. And according to the institution of the collection, which consists of the central tax, the tax administered by the central government and regional tax, namely taxes administered by the Regional Government. There are constraints in tax collection in general, both central taxes and local taxes which can weaken tax collection, such constraints, among others, are the various laws and regulations that are often inconsistent with the law. - The draw, lack of guidance between local taxes and national taxes, databases that are still far from international standards, weak law enforcement (law enforcement) against compliance paying taxes for state administrators, lack or absence of public awareness [16]. The legal basis for collecting local taxes is UUN number 28 of 2009 concerning Regional Taxes and Regional Retribution. In Article 2 of Law Number 28 of 2009, the regional tax is divided into two types and several tax objects, namely the kind of provincial tax consisting of motor vehicle tax, motor vehicle name transfer, motor vehicle fuel tax, surface water tax, cigarette tax. Regency/city tax consists of hotel tax, restaurant tax, entertainment tax, advertisement tax, street lighting tax, non-metal and rock mineral tax, parking tax, groundwater tax, swallow nest tax, land and rural and urban building tax, acquisition fee land and building rights.

Property Tax

In Article 1 of Law Number 28 (2009) the earth is defined as the surface of the earth which includes land and inland and sea waters of the Regency / city region. Whereas the building is a technical construction planted or fixed permanently on land and inland and sea waters. The tax subject in the Land and Building Tax is a person or entity that has a right to the earth, and benefits from the surface, and has control over, and benefits from the building [17]. The objects of land tax and rural and urban buildings are earth and buildings that are owned, controlled, and utilized by individuals or entities, except for areas used for plantation, forestry and mining business activities [17]. According to Law Number 28 (2009), Article 77 Tax Objects that are not subject to Land and Rural and Urban Building Taxes are tax objects used by the Government and Regions for the administration of government. Used solely to serve the public interest in the fields of worship, social, health, education and national culture, which is not intended to gain profit. Used for graves, ancient relics, or similar. It is a protected forest, nature reserve forest, tourism forest, national park, grazing land controlled by the

village, and state land that has not been encumbered by a right. Used by diplomatic and consular representatives based on reciprocal treatment principles. Used by agencies or representatives of international institutions stipulated by the Minister of Finance Regulation. Land and Rural and Urban Buildings Taxes are Taxes on Earth and or Buildings that are owned, controlled, and utilized by individuals or entities, except for areas used in plantation, forestry and mining business activities [18]. What is meant by the Earth is the surface of the earth which includes the land and inland and sea waters of the regency/city region. Whereas what is expected by Buildings is the technical construction that is planted or placed permanently on land and or inland and or sea waters. PBB-P2 is a type of district/city tax that is applied based on Law 28 (2009).

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted at the BP2RD Ternate City. In this case, it is directly related to the object of PBB-P2 service research in BP2RD. One of the reasons that surfaced for the choice of the theme of this Thesis was associated with the PBB-P2 service system. This research was collecting data about actual problems about the symptoms that occur in the field, then through this descriptive method will be given a precise and systematic description by researching, collecting, compiling and analyzing data or problems related to measuring government performance and PBB-P2 Services in the BP2RD Ternate. Primary data is obtained through direct interviews with informants selected according to the quality and quantity of data needed. Whereas secondary data is obtained through literature, legislation, websites on the internet and related documents, to get concepts that can provide an overview of various dimensions of commitment, knowledge, skills and specific attitudes and experiences that support the realization of targets regarding government performance in PBB-P2 of BP2RD Ternate City. Furthermore, the data were analyzed according to Miles and Huberman (2013) [19], through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Service Performance of BP2RD Ternate City

The Performance of the Ternate City Tax and Retribution Management Agency Especially the Management and Payment Services for Land and Rural and Urban Buildings Taxes (PBB-P2) are exciting to discuss, due to various interesting problems faced by BP2RD itself and the communities that some people have to date. Those who do not know the procedures and risks or benefits of PBB-P2. To measure the performance of the government in providing services to the community, there are several things that need to be a concern for the government itself in providing its services, as well as the community as users of services, because on the one hand there is a goal of public organizations that must be achieved, but at the same time the interests of the public as well become one of the variables to measure the success of government performance. This means that if the interests and satisfaction of the community as a service user have been achieved, then there is the success of the government's performance. Assessment of the performance of the public bureaucracy is not enough to be done by using indicators that are attached to the Government,

such as efficiency and effectiveness, but also must be seen from indicators that are attached to service users, such as service user satisfaction, accountability and responsiveness [9]. Inefficiency, it relates to the success of public service organizations in obtaining profits and the results of their services by utilizing the factors of production and considerations derived from economic rationality. In this regard, the Ternate City Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency seek to achieve profits as a source of local revenue (PAD). The Ternate City Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency, in addition to providing PBB-P2 services, BP2RD also sought to collect PBB-P2 to increase PAD. Effectiveness is different from Efficiency if efficiency is the minimum use of resources to achieve optimum results. Efficiency assumes that the true goals have been determined and try to find the best ways to achieve these goals. Efficiency can only be evaluated with relative assessments, comparing the input and output received. However, effectiveness is the achievement of the right objectives or choosing the right goals from a series of alternatives or choice of ways and determining the choice of several other choices. Effectiveness is also interpreted as a measurement of success in achieving predetermined goals. Meanwhile, BP2RD of Ternate City, if viewed from the side of budget usage, the performance of BP2RD of Ternate City has not been maximized, it can be seen from the budget ceiling in 2017 fiscal year from the Regional Expenditure Budget (APBD) of IDR. 24,934,297,990, but realized amounted to IDR 23,352,823,245, the remaining budget ceiling of IDR 1,181,474,745. Services provided to taxpayers by the BP2RD are still discriminatory, and unfair, because they always prioritize people they know, even though they know, but those who come first must be served, and not vice versa. Facilities and infrastructure, regarding the implementation of public services, can support the duties of employees to improve their performance. Facilities in the form of buildings, availability of operational transportation, adequate and infrastructure in the form of tables, chairs, computers, office stationery and other facilities that are directly related to employee routine activities in the office. Provision of infrastructure has met the needs of BP2RD employees in Ternate City. After observing the researchers, the facilities provided by the Ternate City BP2RD for the officer have been very sufficient as well as the facilities offered to taxpayers. Productivity measures not only the level of efficiency but also the effectiveness of service. Productivity is generally understood as input and output. The performance of the BP2RD Ternate City if viewed from the side of the tax collection has been maximized, and it can be seen from the revenue target. To measure the quality of public services as an indicator of the performance of public services, is the satisfaction of consumers or the satisfaction of the community as users of public services, in this connection several sources that I met as informants. In order for the service to be more quality, faster, younger, and the satisfaction of the community as a customer is more secure, the BP2RD Ternate City has tried in various ways, including utilizing information technology facilities, so that all communities can access information related to the management PBB-P2 wherever they are, does not have to be in the office, but at home the community can obtain the information. BP2RD service quality is not good enough to be seen in the presence of several taxpayers who feel they have not been served because there is no queue, so the service provided to the public as a taxpayer looks

favoritism. Responsiveness is the ability of an organization to recognize the needs of the community, develop agenda and priority services, develop public service programs following the needs and aspirations of the community. In brief, responsiveness here refers to the alignment of service programs and activities with the needs and expectations of the community. An organization that has low reactivity by itself the service user community will assume that the performance of the organization is weak. Responsiveness is included as one of the performance indicators because the essence of responsiveness describes directly the ability of BP2RD to carry out its performance to overcome, respond to and fulfill the needs, complaints, demands and aspirations of the community in handling problems in PBB-P2 management. The existence of Law No. 25 (2009) concerning public services makes community bargaining power higher than the provider. The good and bad performance that was first seen was how the organization's ability to respond to any complaints, aspirations, suggestions, or criticisms directed at the organization. There is still a delay in the distribution of debt tax notification (SPPT) in the small town so that many people complain about the PBB-P2 service arrangement. Explain whether the implementation of public organizations is carried out following the correct administrative principles or following organizational policies, both explicit and implicit. The community wants services that are not many requirements because of the many requirements, so it seems that the PBB-P2 management is too complicated. The demands of the people that have developed so far want every government institution that uses and implements the budget gives the accountability person to the party who provides the mandate and the people related to the activity program and the budget used. Other public demands are that in the form of national government regulation or policy that requires all government agencies/institutions to provide accountability at the end of each fiscal year, this is carried out as an effort to realize good governance. Public accountability refers to how much the policies and activities of public organizations are subject to political officials chosen by the people. In this connection, the Ternate City Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency always makes government institutional performance accountability report (LAKIP) This theme is then conveyed to the Mayor of Ternate through Regional Development and Research Development Planning Agency, and then the Mayor prepares a Regional Accountability Report that will be submitted to DPRD, as the overall accountability report of the regional government. Every performance accountability report is always put forward by the government so that the officer can also be more responsible in carrying out its duties.

Factors affecting performance

The function of the structure in an organization is to provide information to all human beings who are members to know the activities or work that must be done, consulted or responsible to whom, so that the process of cooperation towards achieving organizational goals can be realized following the deliberate planning. Clarity in the description of the organizational structure will provide convenience for leaders to distribute positions to the right person so that the effectiveness and effectiveness can be realized. Structural deviations often occur in the Government, and some offices/agencies hold two positions at once and different basic tasks and functions so that the service/agency performance is not running optimally.

Until now the BP2RD Ternate City has never experienced Structural Deviation, structural deviations occur if less trust a leader to his subordinates. In the process of making public policy, the government requires a model in formulating policy, with the existence of this model public policy making can be done to take a decision or opinion from various parties. This model can also help government work in understanding complex public policies, thus facilitating the task of the government in seeking to know how the process of formulating or implementing the public policy process. Leadership is the process of influencing or giving examples by leaders to their followers to achieve organizational goals. Leadership is the ability to change others with a sense of enthusiasm for the achievement of a predetermined goal [20]. Leadership is a human factor that binds a group together and pushes them towards a goal. The role of leadership is a leader or manager whose ability to improve focuses on developing employee skills to enhance the quality of employee performance. The role is the extent to which the role is seen as necessary for the overall success of the implementation of a high level of significance. The perceived role will be associated with implementation responsibilities, control of the skills carried out by the leader (supervisor/manager) in other words emphasizing the development of individual skills and abilities. This is an attempt to influence performance by ensuring that employees have the skills and capabilities that enable the growth of excellent performance. Skill control includes setting goals for the level of expertise and abilities that employees must possess, be monitoring their skills and abilities, guiding the purpose of improvement needed, giving rewards and penalties to employees from their level of expertise and knowledge [21]. One of the most critical tasks of a leader is to determine the best for the organization and its members. But in making decisions, sometimes the leader also faces a dilemma and seems to be at a crossroads. Especially if the choices make you have to sacrifice the interests of others or provide risks that will harm the team. But sometimes difficult decisions must be taken to achieve common goals. Sometimes leaders turn out to make wrong decisions and harm the organization. But believe in making mistakes in making decisions is still better than not taking any action at all. Leaders are individuals who do the process of influencing a group or organization to achieve a goal that has been mutually agreed upon, while leadership is a characteristic that is applied by individuals who act as leaders to influence group members to achieve goals and objectives that have been mutually agreed upon. There are at least four different leadership styles that are applied by a leader so that each member wants to work according to his direction. Here are the four leadership styles. Trust is someone's willingness to rely on others where we have confidence in him. Trust is a mental condition based on one's situation and social context. Leaders need to be trusted by their followers because trust is a mortar (mortar) that binds subordinates to their leaders. Trust in leaders has a positive correlation with various outcomes such as organizational membership behavior, performance and satisfaction and within the organization, only certain people are entitled to the trust of a leader. Actors (bureaucrats) are the determining factors other than the system and policies that have been issued. Many people will say, in the end, human resources is the one who runs the system. Many aspects of the government's downturn in Indonesia all lead to human resources. Indications of low human resources are at least

reflected in three things, namely welfare, reward and punishment. Human resources have a significant role in an organization. Especially in the face of this global era, organizations will be faced with competencies both nationally and internationally. Human resources are also the essential asset and function as capital in a business organization, the capital referred to here is nonfinancial capital that can be used as a real potential physically and non-physically in realizing an organizational existence. Improving the quality of effectiveness and efficiency of organizational activities depends not only on the equipment contained in the office such as sophisticated and modern machines, significant capital, and the quality of quality raw materials. All of these factors are meaningless without the support of excellent and useful human resources. One way to effectively improve human resources is by motivation, training and work development, compensation and promotion. This method will make human resources in the office useful.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In general, the government's performance in the Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency in 2017 has not been maximized, and it can be seen from the BP2RD budget ceiling that reaches IDR. 24,934,297,990, but only IDR. 23,352,823,245, while the remaining budget ceiling is IDR. 1,581,474,745. There is still a lack of community participation in the management and PBB-P2 payments so that there are still many arrears from year to year. There is still a lack of socialization so that some people do not understand the benefits and risks of not paying PBB-P2.

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